

Trust Me; I Know What I Am Doing. Does Specialist Training Reduce Preference Reversals in Decision Making for Others?

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Preference reversals refer to the situation that people prefer A over B in one exercise or situation, but B over A in another. These reversals have been shown quite common, both for decisions for oneself and others. However, they pose multiple problems, also in the field of health care, for instance when dealing with treatment choices or with health state valuations. This paper examines if people with specialist training, e.g. in the field of medicine or finance, show fewer preferences reversals in their respective areas of expertise. Furthermore, we investigate different approaches to reduce the degree of preference reversals in the context of decision making for others.

Methods: We used a sample (N=245) of medical and business administration/economics students, asking about medical and financial decision making for others. Respondents had to choose between two risky options on how to treat a patient with a terminal condition in the medical domain and evaluated both options against a certainty equivalent later on. A similar set of questions was used in the financial domain where respondents had to make investment decisions for others. Additionally, we investigated if describing risk in natural frequencies and the use of choice lists for the valuation task reduced the rate of preference reversals in both settings.

Results: Preliminary results indicate that people with specialist training show fewer preference reversals in their area of expertise. Preference reversals were 6.2 percentage points lower for medical students in the health care setting (59.4%), compared to the financial setting (65.6%). Economics and business students showed a rate of preference reversal that was 14.6 percentage points lower in the financial setting (44.4%) than in the health care setting (59.0%). The results further suggest that choice lists and natural frequencies reduced the degree of preference reversals in the financial setting and that choice lists reduced the degree of reversals in the health care setting. The results from logistic mixed effects regressions substantiate these findings. We observe that preference reversals are more likely to occur: i) for medical students, ii) in the health care scenario, and iii) for open valuation questions. Describing risks in natural frequencies did not affect the degree of preference reversals. We also observe several significant interaction terms, which indicate that familiarity with the domain (i.e. medical or financial) reduced the likelihood of preference reversals.

Conclusion: Preference reversals are an important problem in estimating preferences. This problem seems to be more substantial when people are unfamiliar with the domain they are asked about. This highlights the importance and effects of specialist training. Using choice lists to simplify valuation tasks seems to help respondents to state more consistent preferences across procedures.